

Additional file 4: Results of day 5

(A) Study participants scored the pain they experienced during the ultrasound-guided inguinal lymph node biopsy on a five point Likert scale from 1 'not painful' to 5 'very painful' compared to venipuncture on day 5 after the biopsy procedure. The majority (94%) of responders scored either 1 or 2. (B) Study participants reported their willingness to undergo a second biopsy and to encourage someone else to participate in a similar study by choosing yes, no or neutral. The majority of all responders was willing to undergo a second biopsy (68%) and almost half of the participants was willing to encourage someone else (44%). Overall includes RA, RA-risk and HC individuals. RA, rheumatoid arthritis patients; RA-risk, individuals at risk for developing RA; HC, healthy controls.